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Table with columns for gene ID, coordinates, gene name, and description. The table contains multiple rows of data, including entries like ENSG0000018463, ENSG0000018462, ENSG0000018461, etc., with corresponding genomic coordinates and gene names such as RFX5, RFX5-AS1, RFX5-AS2, etc.



































































































































